

The Unjournal • All unjournal evaluation content

Evaluation 2 of "A systematic review and meta analysis of social safety nets, women's economic achievements and agency"

Rachel Sabates-Wheeler¹

¹Institute of Development Studies

Published on: Sep 16, 2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21428/d28e8e57.eed9fb5a/dd31b232>

License: [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC-BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

